

Robot Perception through Wearable Sensors: Decoding Grasping for Human-Robot Hand-Over

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Abstract—Human-robot interaction represents the cornerstone for the full development of Industry 4.0 and 5.0 paradigms, that rely on this cooperation in order to develop more efficient and flexible production lines. In this context, the human-robot hand-over plays a crucial role and many approaches were introduced to plan and control this task, including the less investigated decoding of human muscles activity. Hence, the design of reliable myoelectric human-robot interfaces is a point of primary interest. This paper investigates the use of a wearable device, i.e. an armband, for achieving a robust detection of several human grasping gestures. An evaluation of the most useful features, belonging to three different computational domains, is also proposed. Outcomes showed that high recognition performance can be achieved with limited computational burden, which is crucial when dealing with real-time demands in collaborative task.

Index Terms—Human-Robot interaction, Hand-Over, Pattern recognition, Myoelectric signal, Grasping

I. INTRODUCTION

Smart factories, where work is managed through the cooperation between human and robots [1], are paramount for the development of Industry 4.0 and 5.0 paradigms. The human-robot (HR) coexistence forms the basis for an effective implementation of the aforementioned paradigms [1]. Furthermore, to increase productivity, human should cooperate with a collaborative robot (cobot) which not only shares the workspace with humans, but also interacts with the latter through contact or contactless actions [1]. This has opened many research opportunities in the HR collaboration (HRC) field.

New sensing technologies have been developed to improve the perception of both cobots and traditional industrial manipulators [1], [2]. Common strategies involve the use of RGB—Depth cameras, proximity sensors, laser scanners or force sensors [1], [2]. However, wearable sensors, i.e. inertial measurement units, surface electromyographic (sEMG), and electroencephalographic probes, can be valuable in the perception of the human intent of motion [1], [3]. In particular, the use of sEMG signals has shown promising results not only in the control of mobile robots, but also in the design of control architectures for various HRC tasks [3], [4].

Among the collaborative tasks that can take place in a smart factory, the HR hand-over represents an important example of

HRC for objects assembling. In [3], hand gesture classification models through sEMG signals were employed to control HR hand-over tasks. Indeed, sEMG data allow to collect information regarding the force exchanged between the human and the object involved in the interaction. Furthermore, gesture recognition through sEMG can overcome some limitations of vision systems such as object occlusion, lighting changes and the development of hand kinematic models required for a good hand pose recognition.

However, the investigation of sEMG-based control architectures for HRC deserves further attention, as only a few models and features have been yet taken into account. For instance, only the standard deviation of the sEMG signals and hidden Markov models were used in [3]. Therefore, the present study investigates the role of possible sEMG features for the design of pattern recognition architectures in HR objects hand-over.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The investigation of additional sEMG features useful for HR objects hand-over was conducted as follows. Ten able-bodied, right-handed subjects were recruited for the study (age 27.3 ± 2.1 years), without any neurological or upper limbs pathologies which could affect motion. All the subjects signed written informed consent prior the beginning of the test and the experimental procedure was approved by the local expert committee, in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki [5]. Each user was instrumented with a single MYO armband which recorded the muscle activity of the dominant forearm through 8 pods with a sampling frequency of 200 Hz. Subjects were required to perform four set of grasping movements (Fig. 1). Each grasp movement was repeated 6 times alternating resting and motion phases by periods of 3 s.

For each user, signals were high-pass filtered by a 2nd order Butterworth filter with a cut-off frequency of 10 Hz to remove low frequency components due to possible sensor displacements. Then, for each grasp movement, muscle activation epochs were identified and segmented with respect to resting phases in order to proceed with feature extraction step. Such epochs were windowed through a sliding window of 500 ms without overlap [3], [5]. Hudgins (H) and Du (D) feature sets were computed [5]. Moreover, other 4 frequency domain (F) features, i.e. mean and median frequency, total and mean

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the use of sEMG wearable sensors in the design of object hand grasp recognition for hand-over tasks in HRC. Grasping gestures are large grasping (LG), small grasping (SG), ring grasping (RG), and pinch grasping (PG).

spectral power were considered. Also, 2 signal complexity descriptors i.e. fuzzy and permutation entropy (FEn and PEn) were computed to add domains of information representation.

Linear discriminant analysis (LDA) was selected as model for grasp inference, since it demonstrated excellent performances [6]. Five-fold cross validation was used to train and test LDA models with the following four different feature set: H, D, H and D (HD), HD and F (HDF). Further, FEn and PEn were included in each set, since they have shown to boost classifier performances [5].

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mean accuracy values for the ten subjects are shown in Table I. Each feature set showed an accuracy not lower than 85%. Still, the best performance was obtained for the HDF set, where entropy features showed remarkable clustering properties for all grasping gestures (Fig. 2). Note that the feature aggregation employed guaranteed also a reduction in the variance of the LDA performances, indicating that the selected features contributed to generate a reliable feature space for the identification of human hand grasps. The accuracy obtained is of the same order as that reported in [3], so that the proposed model can be included in the control architecture for HR interaction. The study confirms the possibility of using wearable sensors for the realization of intelligent architectures that can be embedded in hierarchical control schemes. Moreover, a simple model such as the LDA showed equal or superior performances to more complex artificial intelligent systems, whether proper information is extracted from the sEMG signals [6]. This represents an important aspect toward the realization of cobot control. Indeed one of the advantages of using wearable motion sensors is their ability to detect human intention. This is a key point for the implementation of active decision systems, e.g., to ensure the acceptance or rejection of the object exchanged in hand-over [3]. A limitation of the study is the reduced number of grasp movements and the real-time validation. However, it should be noticed that the presented myoelectric control architecture performed well also when trained with a larger number of gestures [6]. Hence, attention will be provided to the generalization of hand-over object grasping and to the embedding of such models, as suggested in [3].

Fig. 2. Clustering of FEn and PEn features for each grasping gesture.

TABLE I
MEAN ACCURACY (%) OBTAINED IN FIVE-FOLD CROSS VALIDATION AVERAGED AMONG THE TEN SUBJECTS WITH RESPECT TO EACH FEATURE SET.

Feature Set			
H	D	HD	HDF
88.7 ± 8.3	86.6 ± 8.7	91.0 ± 4.6	94.7 ± 2.3

IV. CONCLUSION

Wearable sensors can be a viable alternative to more classical approaches, such as cameras, in HR hand-over. Reliable performance was achieved with typical machine learning models when appropriate features were extracted from the sEMG signals. This may be beneficial for their embedding into broader control policies required in new industrial paradigms.

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